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CRIME SCENE INVESTIGATION, OBJECTS AND DOCUMENTS SAMPLING, SEARCH AND EVIDENCE COLLECTION DURING INVESTIGATION OF THE SMUGGLING OF MIGRANTS OFFENCE

The crime scene investigation, the examination of physical evidence - objects and documents -, as well as searches and evidence collection, are essential procedural actions for the evidence collection and administration of evidence in the investigation of the organized migrant smuggling. For this reason, this present study explores the specifics and particularities of these actions from a forensic perspective. The article is not limited only to theoretical aspects, but also integrates an extensive analysis of current judicial practice, relating it to the scientific foundations.

The main objective of the scientific article was to examine the tactics applied in the conduct of these procedural actions, as well as to identify legislative gaps and inconsistencies in the application of judicial practice. Ultimately, the research aims to provide practical recommendations, based on a scientific approach, to support the prosecution authorities. The effective implementation of these recommendations would contribute to improving the process of investigating the organization of irregular migration, facilitating the work of prosecution authorities and strengthening the state's obligations in the fight against crime.

Keywords: crime scene investigation, physical evidence, search, evidence collection, migrant smuggling.

INVESTIGAREA SCENEI CRIMEI, EȘANȚIONAREA OBIECTELOR ȘI DOCUMENTELOR, CĂUTAREA ȘI CULEGEREA PROBELOR ÎN TIMPUL INVESTIGĂRII INFRAȚIUNII DE CONTRABANDĂ DE MIGRANȚI

Cercetarea locului faptei, examinarea probelor fizice - obiecte și documente -, precum și perchezițiile și colectarea probelor, sunt acțiuni procedurale esențiale pentru colectarea probelor și administrarea probelor în cercetarea traficului organizat de migranți. Din acest motiv, studiul de față explorează specificul și particularitățile acestor acțiuni din perspectivă criminalistică. Articolul nu se limitează doar la aspectele teoretice, ci integrează și o analiză amplă a practicii judiciare actuale, raportând-o la fundamentele științifice.

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Obiectivul principal al articolului științific a fost de a examina tacticile aplicate în desfășurarea acestor acțiuni procedurale, precum și de a identifica lacunele și inconsecvențele legislative în aplicarea practicii judiciare. În cele din urmă, cercetarea își propune să ofere recomandări practice, bazate pe o abordare științifică, pentru a sprijini autoritățile de urmărire penală. Implementarea efectivă a acestor recomandări ar contribui la îmbunătățirea procesului de investigare a organizării migrației ilegale, la facilitarea activității organelor de urmărire penală și la consolidarea obligațiilor statului în lupta împotriva criminalității.

Cuvinte-cheie: investigarea locului crimei, probe fizice, căutare, colectarea probelor, contra-banda de migrați.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the investigation of the organization of migrant smuggling, procedural actions such as crime scene investigation, examination of objects and documents, searches and evidence collections, although not always frequently applied, are essential for obtaining evidence and clarifying the circumstances of the crimes. The tactics of conducting these actions play a central role in ensuring their effectiveness, directly contributing to the identification and prosecution of persons involved in migrant smuggling networks.

The crime scene investigation, although not carried out in all cases, remains an important step when applied, allowing for thorough documentation and analysis of the relevant elements. The examination of objects and documents, as well as searches and evidence collections, are tactics which, when used, ensure the evidence collection and protection of evidence necessary to reconstruct the modus operandi of criminal networks.

The importance of these procedural actions, even if they are not uniformly applied in all investigations, lies in their ability to assist prosecution authorities in effectively combating irregular migration. A well-informed tactical approach, even in the selective use of these methods, contributes to strengthening the State's capacity to ensure a full and fair justice process.

2. METHODOLOGY

Theoretical, normative and empirical materials were used in the elaboration of this publication. Also, the analysis of the treated subject was carried out by applying various methods of scientific research, specific to forensic theory and doctrine, including: logical method, deduction and induction, comparative analysis, systemic analysis, among others. The theoretical-legal basis of this scientific article is constituted by the normative regulations in the field of criminal procedure and forensic, with emphasis on crime scene investigation, examination of objects and documents, searches and evidence collections.

3. DISCUSSIONS

Before proceeding to the exposition of the subject at hand we would like to shed some light. The crime scene investigation should not be confused with the investigation (examination) of objects and documents, which, in our opinion, should be a separate procedural and forensic tactical action. This subject may raise discussion and controversy, because according to Art. 118 para. (1) CPP, *„For the purpose of discovering and collecting traces of the offense, material means of evidence to establish the circumstances of the offense or other circumstances that are relevant to the case, the prosecuting body shall conduct crime scene search of land, rooms, objects, documents, computer systems or computer data*

storage media, animals, human or animal corpses". In other words, on-the-spot searches of documents, objects, etc. are also possible. We are not against this provision, but when on-the-spot searches of land or premises are carried out and objects or documents are found, they may also be searched (examined) as part of the on-the-spot search. This requirement is also reflected in the provisions of Article 118(1)(b) and (c) of the Rules of Procedure. (4), (5) and (7) CPC. How do we proceed when objects and documents are seized either as a result of the on-the-spot investigation, or by evidence collection under Article 126 CPP, search, etc.? In these cases, will the search (examination) of these objects and documents be carried out, or will the crime scene search be carried out or continued?

According to the legal dictionary, „crime scene - an area of land or a certain enclosure, spatially and temporally related to the crime under investigation, in the true sense of the word, crime scene means the area where traces of the crime were discovered. However, it should be borne in mind that the crime may have been committed elsewhere. For example, the rape took place at the offender's home and the victim's body was found in a well, which has led to a distinction being made in recent literature between the place where the crime was committed (in the example given, the offender's home) and the place of the crime (the well where the body was found)”¹.

It should be noted that the place where the crime was committed and the place of the crime may coincide.

Researchers², also distinguish between the place where the offense was committed and the place of the crime, there being no difference of opinion, i.e. the place of investigation is the place where the criminal act occurred or where the harmful prosecution took place, i.e. the result of this act. However, the respective doctrinarists refer to a territory, room, open land, etc., not to objects or documents.

We support, in this regard, the opinion of Ion Mircea, who states that, „the place of the crime is the perimeter within the limits of which the material evidence created during the commission of the offense is located. Thus, it includes: the land or room where the offense was committed, the place where the result was produced, the surroundings of these places, if they are bearers of traces created during the commission of the offense under investigation”³. He also specifies that, „(...) in the process of on-the-spot investigation, it is necessary to carry out a thorough examination, portion by portion, of the place in question, so that no area is left unexcavated”⁴.

„The on-the-spot investigation is carried out in order to ascertain the circumstances of the commission of the crime, to determine the existence, position and condition of the material means of evidence, to identify the persons who committed the criminal act and other circumstances that are important for the fair resolution of the criminal case”⁵.

¹ Legal Dictionary. Available: <https://legeaz.net/dictionar-juridic/locul-fapteii> [accessed: 14.08.2022].

² Stancu Emilian, *Tratat de criminalistică*, 6th Edition, revised, Universul Juridic Publishing House, Bucharest, 2015, p. 357-358; Crișu Anastasiu, *Drept procesual penal, General Part*, 6th Edition, revised and updated, Hamangiu Publishing House, Bucharest, 2022, p. 449-450; Neagu Ion, *Damaschin Mircea, Criminal Procedure Treatise, General Part*, 3rd edition, revised and added, Universul Juridic Publishing House, Bucharest, 2020, p. 593; Doraș Simion, *Criminalistics, Volume II, Tactical Elements*, Central Printing House, Chisinau, 1999, p. 41.

³ Mircea Ion, *Criminalistica*, 2nd Edition, Lumina Lex Publishing House, Bucharest, 2010, p. 226-227.

⁴ Mircea Ion, *Criminalistica*, 2nd Edition, Lumina Lex Publishing House, Bucharest, 2010, p. 226.

⁵ Ostavciuc Dinu, *Odagiu Iurie, Tactics of conducting on-the-spot investigation, Methodical guide for crim-*

In other words, the majority of academics state that the purpose of on-the-spot investigation is the direct perception by the prosecuting authority of the place where the crime was committed, the search, discovery, detection, fixing, taking, lifting and examination of evidence, including the position and condition of the evidence⁶.

In view of the above, in order to avoid ambiguous interpretation of Art. 118 CPP, we propose the introduction of a new rule in the criminal procedure law, defining a new procedural action in its own right - the examination of objects, documents (including computerized data) and official sites or any other type of electronic addresses. Thus, the examination should be carried out separately from the examination in the framework of crime scene investigation, lifting, search, etc.

Following the examination of judicial practice, as mentioned, crime scene investigation in cases of organizing migrant smuggling occupies a volume of 17%. It should also be noted that on-the-spot investigation in these cases is carried out in 32% of the cases examined. In other words, not in all cases of investigation of the organization of migrant smuggling this action was carried out. However, we cannot diminish its importance, which is extremely important from both a procedural-criminal and forensic perspective, being considered by most researchers and practitioners as an essential action and evidentiary procedure for establishing the truth in a criminal case⁷.

For example, in a case⁸, the prosecution body investigating the organization of migrant smuggling by an organized criminal group, consisting of citizens of the Republic of Moldova and Ukraine, who, with the aim of obtaining financial benefit in exchange for money, organized the illegal entry on the territory of the Republic of Moldova of male citizens of Ukraine, who, due to the armed conflict on the territory of Ukraine, fell under the restriction to leave the country. „By the finding report of 18.03.2022 it was established that on 18.03.2022, around 20.00, from behind the border sign 0754/14, the means of transport OV, license plate XXX 000, at the wheel of which was PR citizen, and with him (...) four citizens of Ukraine (...)”. Thanks to the on-the-spot investigation, the prosecutor was able to determine the exact place of crossing the state border, the means and route of crossing, the time of committing the crime, the time of the crime, the traces of the crossing, the identification of witnesses (victims) and some perpetrators, etc. Without this procedural action, the prosecutor could risk not discover the crime or obtain indisputable evidence.

In these cases, the on-the-spot investigation is not a simple prosecution action, but an activity of the utmost importance of an immediate and irreplaceable nature, in many cases almost impossible to repeat under the same conditions and with the same results⁹.

inal investigation officers, Legal Collection of the „Stefan cel Mare” Academy of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Moldova, Cartea Militară Publishing House, Chisinau, 2020, p. 4.

⁶ Bercheșan Vasile, *Cercetarea penală*, Icar Publishing House, Bucharest, 2001, p. 251; Ciopraga Aurel, *Tratat de tactică criminalistică*, Gama Publishing House, Iași, 1996, p. 31; Stancu Emilian, *Tratat de criminalistică*, Universul Juridic Publishing House, Bucharest, 2002, p. 308.

⁷ Antoniu George, *Explicații teoretice ale Codului de procedură penală*, Parte generală, volume I, Romanian Academy Publishing House, Bucharest, 1975, p. 294; Stancu Emilian, *Tratat de criminalistică*, 5th edition, revised and added, Universul Juridic Publishing House, Bucharest, 2010, p. 359.

⁸ Judgment of the Cahul District Court, Central Office of 11.10.2022, issued in Case no. 1-327/2022. Available: https://jch.instante.justice.md/ro/pigd_integration/pdf/34e3cc54-5b66-4e80-a615-b5b6f892e7c4 [accessed: 06.08.2024].

⁹ Bercheșan Vasile, *Criminal Investigation (Criminalistics - theory and practice)*, Complete Guide to Crimi-

For example, an organized criminal group, in order to obtain a financial benefit in the amount of 32000 US dollars, organized the illegal entry into the territory of the Republic of Moldova of 4 citizens of Ukraine, who are neither citizens nor residents of the Republic of Moldova. Subsequently, by circumventing the border control, in an organized manner, the citizens of Ukraine, accompanied by the guide BF, illegally crossed the state border of the Republic of Moldova on foot, in the direction XXX, where they were detained by the employees of the Border Police of the Republic of Moldova, near the village YYY¹⁰.

Due to the fact that the on-the-spot investigation was carried out immediately, in conditions appropriate to the case, the territory and the direction of the crossing were examined, and the exact place of the commission of the offense was determined, implicitly by indicating the border sign, which indicates the direct intention of illegal crossing. If the investigation was not carried out on the spot, we consider that the prosecuting body did not administer evidence to prove that migrant smuggling was organized. Otherwise, the actions could have been considered as mere illegal crossing of the state border (Article 362 CP).

We note that on-the-spot searches in cases of organized irregular migration should be carried out as soon as the need arises. This tactical requirement aims to ensure maximum preservation of objects and influences the efficiency and results of the examination. The above example shows that immediate action yields positive results in the investigation of such crimes, but in cases where the crime scene search is delayed, difficulties, sometimes insurmountable, may arise.

Another example in this regard is the case of organization of migrant smuggling, where the criminal prosecution body, by the minutes of crime scene investigation with illustrative plan, drawn up on 17 November 2023, fixed the place on the bank of the Prut River where 5 (five) foreign citizens (from India) without documents were found, this place being at the border sign 1079 upstream 50 meters at a distance of 10 meters from the bank of the Prut River in the protection strip¹¹.

The conducted analysis shows that the tactical peculiarities of the crime scene investigation provide the necessary information for organizing the investigation, determining the possible directions of investigation, formulating forensic versions of the persons involved in organizing migrant smuggling and many other circumstances necessary for a complete and objective investigation. The study of the criminal cases showed that on-the-spot investigation is carried out in the majority of cases of apprehension of illegal migrants when crossing the state border, either at the Border Crossing Point or by evading border control, or by evading border control. In all other criminal cases, on-the-spot investigation is not carried out.

By the Sentence of the Comrat Court of Comrat, Ciadir-Lunga branch¹², ZV was

nal Investigation. Editura și tipografia ICAR, București, 2002, p. 253.

¹⁰ Judgment of the Comrat Court, Ciadir-Lunga district, dated 30.05.2024, issued in Case No. 1-28/2024. Disponibilă: https://jco.instante.justice.md/pigd_integration/pdf/675da13f-3005-4011-a080-c8c956216562 [accesată: 06.08.2024].

¹¹ Judgment of the Ungheni Court of 08.07.2024 (p. 11), issued in Case no. 1-84/2024. Available: https://jun.instante.justice.md/ro/pigd_integration/pdf/33152dcb-cfb4-40e5-ae6e-387ba92e6de9 [accessed: 07.08.2024].

¹² Judgment of the Comrat Court of Comrat, Ciadir-Lunga, dated 29.08.2023, issued in Case No. 1-11/2023.

convicted of organizing migrant smuggling of 2 citizens of Ukraine in the amount of 8000 USD. Thanks to the crime scene investigation, the prosecutor was able to determine the further directions of the investigation, submitted the appropriate versions and planned to carry out further procedural actions, including special investigative measures. Thus, the results of the on-the-spot investigation provided the basis for interception and recording of communications and/or images, thanks to which not only evidence of guilt was obtained, but also other participants in the crime could be identified. At the same time, the prosecution body identified witnesses (victims) of the crime, from whom objects were taken, which were subsequently subjected to examination, the results of which were essential in proving the guilt of the defendant.

A particular feature of the on-the-spot investigation is the establishment, identification and evidence collection of the means and instruments of the crime. This particularity, especially in the case of investigating the organization of migrant smuggling, enables the prosecuting body not only to establish the place of commission of the crime, to identify the perpetrators and witnesses (victims), but also to prove their intention to cross the state border illegally, the roles of each participant in the commission of the crime, implicitly when it is committed by an organized criminal group (the role of each of them will be identified: the traveller, the driver, the person who took the money, the person who arranges their accommodation, etc.), identifying the method of committing the crime, etc.

An eloquent example may serve the materials of the criminal case in which *„4 citizens of the Republic of Moldova, by prior agreement with foreign persons unidentified by the prosecuting body, acting within an organized criminal group, created in advance for the commission of the crime of organizing migrant smuggling, with roles being distributed among the members of the respective meeting, in order to obtain direct financial gain, they organized the illegal exit from the territory of the Republic of Moldova, with a view to illegal transit through the territory of Romania and illegal entry into the territory of the Shengen countries of citizens of Armenia, who are neither citizens nor residents of this state, by means of illegal crossing of the state border of the Republic of Moldova, evading border control”*¹³. As a result of the on-the-spot investigation the following objects could be determined, fixed and seized: the car with which the citizens of Armenia were transported to the border area, the boat with which they intended to cross the Nistru River (to illegally cross the state border), the temporary placement of the victims in an abandoned building near the border sign 1175 in the direction of the village Tochile-Răducani, Leova rayon, Republic of Moldova, from where they were picked up by another person (as a guide), the intention to illegally cross the state border in the direction of the village Broscoștești, Romania.

Thus, during the crime scene investigation of the rooms used as accommodation or for temporary detention of illegal migrants, it is necessary to pay attention to the presence and number of places for sleeping, eating, the degree of their equipment, kitchen utensils, the presence and nature of food, toiletries, personal hygiene items, clothing, money, identity documents of foreign citizens; to focus on such documents, such as diaries, receipts,

Disponibilă: https://jco.instante.justice.md/pigd_integration/pdf/b7982f7e-8226-4da7-9158-ce65b-b86a6e1 [accesată: 06.10.2023].

¹³ Judgment of the Cimislia District Court, Central Office, dated 27.02.2018, issued in Case No. 1-27/18. Available: https://jcm.instante.justice.md/pigd_integration/pdf/dbeb8f40-af1b-e811-80d5-0050568b44c1 [accessed: 04.03.2023].

tickets for various types of transportation, etc.

For example, in a case of organization of migrant smuggling¹⁴, one of the procedural actions carried out was the crime scene investigation, during which the „Evidence of the fund of occupied rooms” for the date of 07.07.2017 in the hotel „Cosmos”, located in mun. Chisinau. Thanks to this procedural action, the prosecuting body established the temporary place of stay of the illegal migrant, the persons who visited him, as well as the time of accommodation and departure from the hotel. These data were important for the prosecution body to carry out other procedural actions, thanks to which the court found the defendant guilty.

When a car is detained at the scene, it is recommended to urgently remove the keys from the engine starter, restrict access to the car to any participants, minimize the risk of an accident while detaining a vehicle with persons (if it is being pursued and on summons does not stop). It is also necessary to use weapons only in extreme cases to stop such a vehicle in which an illegal migrant is being transported in a hidden compartment or using false documents. It is not excluded that medical help may be required during the examination. That is why it is important to pass on this information in an operational manner and to plan actions so that all the necessary specialists can be on the scene immediately.

The analysis carried out shows that in cases concerning the investigation of the organization of migrant smuggling, crime scene investigation can be carried out both at the initial stages or even up to the start of criminal proceedings (by the investigating bodies) and at the later stages of investigation. It is important to consider that these examinations have two main directions. The first direction is the examination to document the traces of detention, use of labor and transportation of illegal migrants and to discover illegal migrants at the scene of the crime. The second direction is the examination to discover the locations used for the accommodation and detention of illegal migrants.

An eloquent example is presented by the materials of the criminal case no. 2016872026¹⁵, where following the on-the-spot investigation conducted in a hotel in mun. Chisinau, 3 persons of Sri Lankan origin (migrants), passports, telephones, notes, maps, tickets, etc. were found. Thus, due to the correct planning of procedural actions and special investigative measures, one part of the prosecution group apprehended 4 persons at the state border, who intended to cross the country illegally, together with the traveler, i.e. in flagrante delicto, another part of the prosecution group carried out searches and other measures, and a third part carried out crime scene investigation.

Thanks to the undercover agent, it was possible to plan the actions correctly, the authorities reacted quickly, the entire network was apprehended practically in flagrante delicto, material evidence was discovered and collected, victims were identified, etc.

Thus, in cases where there are several perpetrators and victims of migrant smuggling, especially in cases where the intention is to illegally cross the state border of the Republic of Moldova and the exact location of the crossing is unknown, we recommend

¹⁴ Judgment of the Chisinau District Court, Central Office, dated 01.11.2018, issued in Case No. 1-679/2018. Disponibilă: https://jc.instante.justice.md/ro/pigd_integration/pdf/53f5afb6-1de0-e811-80d5-0050568b021b [accesată: 04.04.2024].

¹⁵ Criminal case no. 2016872026, in which the criminal prosecution was initiated on 10.03.2016, on the basis of Art. 362/1, para. (3), letter a) of the Criminal Code, by the criminal prosecution body of the Ministry of Internal Affairs, established within the Border Police Department.

involving a considerable number of law enforcement officers (border guards), due to the large area of the territory under investigation. In addition, before starting this prosecution action, it is advisable to establish a security perimeter around the place to be investigated in order to prevent attempts by illegal immigrants to flee from the place of examination, given their reluctance to contact the authorities due to their illegal presence on the territory of the country.

For example, in 2023, a group of unidentified persons composed of citizens of Ukraine and the Republic of Moldova, previously sharing roles, acting with direct intention, determining criminal activities at the cross-border level and aiming to obtain financial or material benefit, created a criminal scheme according to which, using the Republic of Moldova as a transit zone, they organized migrant smuggling of Ukrainian citizens with illegal crossing of the Moldovan-Ukrainian border and transit of the Republic of Moldova to the Member States of the European Union. Thanks to the involvement of several border police employees, including the state border surveillance equipment, specialists in the field of kinology, and the formation of a security cordon to prevent illegal migrants from escaping, four victims, citizens of Ukraine, were apprehended, and subsequently three perpetrators were arrested and identified by the criminal prosecution¹⁶.

Therefore, it is advisable that the crime scene investigation is carried out with the use of video recording or photography, state border surveillance technique, as this allows not only more complete and objective documentation, in dynamics, of the unfolding of the content and results of the prosecution action, but also the effective use of the obtained materials both in the analysis and evaluation of the available data, as well as in the planning and conduct of the appropriate versions and actions related to their verification. Photographs or video recordings documenting all elements described in the minutes shall be an annex to the minutes. The prosecution officer as well as the members of the prosecution team (if there are any) may watch the recording several times, thus calmly observing details that need to be emphasized and used in the preparation of hearings, verification of statements on the spot, planning and ordering of special investigative measures, etc.

„The crime scene investigation in the case of the organization of migrant smuggling shall be carried out in order to establish the following circumstances, which characterize:

Subject of the crime: number of persons involved in the crime; approximate age of the participants in the crime (adults, minors); their physical data (height, physical strength, etc.); state of health (presence of injuries, physical disabilities); habits; possession of certain skills; profession; data characterizing their mental peculiarities (cruelty, caution, fear, etc.); information on the way of working (if the place of crime is an institution or a business) or lifestyle (if the place of crime is an apartment or a dwelling house);

The object of the crime: what the criminal attack was directed at; what was the direct object of the crime; the physical and mental characteristics of the victim (if the attack was directed against a person); the characteristics of the objects - their gender and individual characteristics (if the attack was directed against things);

The objective side of the crime: when the crime was committed, how the crime was

¹⁶ Criminal case no. 2023870527, in which the criminal prosecution was initiated on 05.05.2023 by the criminal prosecution body established within the General Inspectorate of the Border Police on the basis of Art. 362/1 para. (3) letter a) CP.

committed; the actions of the offenders at the scene of the crime; the circumstances that favored the commission of the crime; the consequences of the crime committed; the existence of a causal link between the actions of the offenders and the consequences produced;

The subjective side of the crime: whether the crime was committed intentionally or negligently; the motives and purposes of the offender”¹⁷.

Search (examination) of objects and documents. When investigating this crime, the examination of documents plays a very important role. The prosecuting authorities must pay special attention to both the physical appearance and the content of these documents, as they may contain false information, which is common in cases of organizing migrant smuggling. Such documents may include employment contracts, pay slips, fictitious employment contracts, forged identity cards and driving licenses, inauthentic visas and other false documents.

«It is important that the examination in these cases is carried out carefully and comprehensively, so that the subsequent analysis can reveal the wrongdoing of the perpetrators. At the same time, it is necessary to pay attention to the following during the examination of papers and documents: deterioration of the paper on which the document was made, loss of gloss in certain places, exfoliation of certain parts of the documents; the presence of gray and yellow stains and micro cracks, the presence of discolorations in the course of the text; unusual arrangement of inscriptions and calligraphic differences; roughness of the lines and thickening of the paper in certain places; mismatch of the stamp on the document with the stamp on the photograph and the marks of stamp printing and others»¹⁸.

Our analysis shows that the examination of objects and documents is carried out in about 84% of cases of investigation of the organization of migrant smuggling. Within the investigation of the organization of migrant smuggling, it is possible to examine clothes or objects found in the temporary accommodation of migrants, after body searches, at the place of apprehension of migrants during the attempt to cross the state border illegally, etc.

Thus, „by the examination report of 18.03.2020, the objects and clothes seized on the basis of the crime scene investigation report of 23.02.2020, from TA’s house, located in or. XXX, village YYY, in the immediate vicinity of the Prut River, where in fact, with the consent of the former, by himself lived cet. PV, namely: footwear and a rubber room, tied with thread and a net, improvised in a boat. From the photo images, annexed to these minutes, it can be seen that a cap, which was with PV, photographed on 22.02.2020 at the time of his apprehension on the territory of Romania near the Prut River, together with 3 other persons of Turkish origin, is the one detected in the dwelling under investigation. Based on the order of 18.03.2020, the objects and clothes subject to examination were recognized as material evidence - corpus delicti”¹⁹.

¹⁷ Биррюков Святослав Юрьевич, Особенности расследования организации незаконной миграции, Диссертация на соискание ученой степени кандидата юридических наук, Волгоград, 2008, с. 142-143.

¹⁸ Ostavciuc Dinu, Odagiu Iurie, *Metodica cercetării organizării migrației ilegale, Ghid metodic pentru ofițerii se urmărire penale*, Colecția juridică a Academiei „Ștefan cel Mare” a Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Moldova, *Cartea Militară Publishing House, Chisinau, 2020, p. 48.*

¹⁹ Judgment of the Hîncești Court, Central Office, dated 21.07.2020, issued in Case no. 1-129/20. Disponibilă: https://jhn.instante.justice.md/ro/pigd_integration/pdf/80651d34-2bd4-4577-a037-74ee750dc98f [21.01.2024].

At the same time, in the cases investigated by us, the object of examination are information carriers containing video footage, photographs, scanned, photographed or World documents, etc.

For example, in a criminal case, it was submitted for examination „*the information carrier of CD type, with video footage from the premises of the hotel „City Center”, mun. Chisinau, 32 Pushkin St., which was recognized as material evidence and annexed to the present criminal case, by the OUP order of 12.02.2024*”. According to the examination, it was possible to identify the persons involved in the organization of migrant smuggling, proof of the perpetrator’s meeting with witnesses (victims), money transmission, etc. Also in the case, „*the examination report of 13.02.2024 was drawn up, according to which on 28.01.2024, at 22.34, in the sights, the car XXX appears in the car XXX moving on Grenoble St. in mun. Chisinau from the direction of the roundabout with Valea Crucii St. and enters the territory of the Peco station „Bemol”, where it parks for about a minute, after which it leaves in the direction from which it came. At 11.35 p.m., a white car, similar to a YYY, enters the territory of the Peco „Bemol” station, where it parks in the place where the XXX car was previously. A group of people and another means of transportation are observed nearby. At 23.54, the car leaves the territory of the Peco station and drives on Grenoble street towards the roundabout with Valea Crucii street. On 29.01.2024, at 07.29, ZZZ enters the Peco „Bemol” station and parks next to a means of transport, which was later determined to be model NNN and belonging to the injured party PR. 4 people get out of the car ZZZZZ, 2 people get out of the car YYY. At 07.36, 5 people get into car ZZZ, and at 07.37 both cars leave the Peco station*”²⁰. Thanks to the evidence collection and examination of the video footage it was possible to prove the meeting between the victims (witnesses) and the perpetrators, the means of transportation in which the migrants were transported, the number and identity of the migrants and the persons involved, where they were brought, by whom and other important circumstances. As a result of the examination it was possible to plan and carry out other procedural actions and special investigative measures.

Various databases managed by the authorities are also examined in the cases investigated. For example, the information on the documents to be submitted to the General Inspectorate for Migration in order to invite a foreigner to the Republic of Moldova; the information on the crossing of the state border by persons and means of transportation, thanks to which it is possible to determine the specific time of crossing of a certain person, the means of transportation with which he crossed, who was the driver and the passengers. An eloquent example can be the examination of the information from the database managed by the Border Police, which found that „*on 21.03.2022, following this procedural action, the prosecution proved the crossing of the state border from the exit to Romania of a means of transportation registered in France*”. At the same time, also in the respective case, following the examination, it was established that „*in the period of time 24.12.2017 - 23.01.2023 and, respectively, 01.01.2022 - 05.06.2023, the person PV crossed the state border*”²¹. As a result of the respective information, the veracity of the witnesses’ statements, the means of transportation with which he was transported, the actual time of the exit of

²⁰ https://jhn.instante.justice.md/ro/pigd_integration/pdf/dd8070aa-5ca4-45c0-90df-2983ddc96251

²¹ Judgment of the Comrat Court, Ciadir-Lunga district, dated 17.08.2023, issued in case no. 1-98/2023. Available: https://jco.instante.justice.md/pigd_integration/pdf/0d51d132-08ad-4bbf-afe0-e67dcaec08d1 [accessed: 06.10.2023].

the accused and the victim (witness) from the country, the direction of the movement and other circumstances relevant to the criminal investigation were established.

Responses received from embassies, Interpol, the Joint Contact Center Galati and other authorities are also subject to examination. This information plays an important role and constitutes evidence in the investigation of the organization of migrant smuggling. It provides the prosecuting authority with information on facts and persons, whether or not certain actions have taken place and by whom, data on documents, annexes to requests, etc.

For example, in a criminal case, on 24.03.2016, it was „*examined the response received from the Vice Consul of the US Embassy, DT, to which were attached the lists of citizens of the Republic of Moldova who applied for a visa to the United States of America, on the basis of participation in sports competitions. The lists of the citizens who applied for the visa are presented on 2 A4 tabs, printed in tabular form, with the data of the applicants (name, surname, year of birth, the championship to which the person declared that he/she is going, as well as the date when the person was refused or accepted). The lists also include cet. GC, who has been accepted to open a visa for the New York Golden Gloves Boxing Tournament in the USA, and cet. SM, who was refused an entry visa to the USA on the grounds that he was going to the same championship to which GC applied. Other participants who applied for a US departure visa for the above-mentioned championship do not appear*”²². On the basis of the reply received and examined, the prosecuting authority proved that the documents submitted for the visa application are false and do not correspond to reality. At the same time, the prosecution body obtained information on the time of submission of the documents, the time of obtaining the visa, the type of documents submitted and by whom they were issued, who is the beneficiary of the visa, the indicated purpose, etc.

Social networks are also subject to examination in order to identify witnesses, victims or even suspects and the content of their profiles. For example, in a criminal case on the fact of the organization of migrant smuggling of citizens of Ukraine, from the state-

²² Judgment of the Chisinau District Court, Central Office, dated 23.06.2017, issued in Case No. 1-268/16. Available: https://jc.instante.justice.md/ro/pigd_integration/pdf/d10369bc-cd58-e711-80d3-0050568b4c47 [accessed: 13.11.2023]. According to the materials of the criminal case, „*at the end of 2014 GC having the intention to go to work in the USA appealed to SN in order to help obtain a visa at the US Embassy in the Republic of Moldova. In order to help obtain a US visa in the name of GC, SN, in his turn, appealed to RG, and the latter to DI, a person who by virtue of the type of activity practiced, wrestling coach in the or. Tiraspol, was competent in the field of finalization of the sets of documents necessary for visa applications at the Embassies and Consulates accredited to the Republic of Moldova. In December 2014, RG in the premises of the Elat Commercial Center, bl. Decebal, 99, mun. Chisinau, in order to help obtain a US visa for GC, under the pretext of GC's participation in the wrestling championship in the city of Chisinau. New York, USA, solicited from the latter funds totaling 4000 euro (...). DI, fabricated a set of documents with distorted data, diplomas and certificates issued in the name of GC, according to which allegedly in the period of 2010-2014 he allegedly participated and occupied various prize-winning places at the boxing and kick-boxing championships organized on the territory of the self-proclaimed Transnistrian republic and is a competitive sportsman. In January 2015, RG and DI handed the aforementioned set of documents to GC to be submitted to the US Embassy in the Republic of Moldova, advising him on how to conduct himself during the interview at the Embassy and supporting the fact that he is an athlete and is going to compete in the USA. Having been instructed by RG and DI, on the basis of the mentioned set of misrepresented documents received from RG and submitted to the US Embassy in the Republic of Moldova, in January 2015 GC obtained visa series K no. 0249749 for departure to the USA, or. New York, the destination being Golden Gloves Boxing Tournament, subsequently on the basis of the said visa, leaving to the USA for work*”.

ments of victims and witnesses, „on 24.03.2022, the profile of the accused AA in social networks Facebook and Instagram was examined, with the participation of the victim AM”²³. The examination found the list of friends, among which another co-perpetrator of the crime was identified, the messages and posts made by the defendant, etc. Therefore, due to that examination, the prosecutor was able to obtain evidence, as well as information on planning and submitting other forensic versions.

There are also situations when the victims (witnesses) of the organization of migrant smuggling present other evidence to the prosecutor, for example, interceptions made personally during the discussions with the perpetrator, from which the criminal stages, the route to be taken, at which stage other members of the criminal group will intervene to take the victims, the directions to be followed by the victims, where they have to cross the border illegally, with whom, etc. For example, in case 1-327/2022, it was found that the prosecuting body, on 28.06.2022, examined „(...) 4 /four/ CDs, with audio recordings submitted by the victims (witnesses) TM, AM, TO and PH (...)”²⁴.

In cases of organization of migrant smuggling, depending on the circumstances, the information provided through the Joint Contact Center Galati of the Ministry of Internal Affairs is requested, obtained and examined, which is specific for the investigation of these types of crimes. Thus, „by the information no. 25/7-369 of 21.02.2020, provided through the Joint Contact Center Galați of the Interior Ministry, it results that the car with registration number XXX is registered in Romania (registration certificate no. YYY dated 04.09.2018) in the name of Turkish citizen SZ, son of AB and AC, CNP: 000000, born (...) in Pazarcik, Turkey, residing in mun. NNNN, str. MMMM, county KKKK, Romania, tourist passport series/number U15109989, valid from 22.12.2017-30.08.2025, temporary residence permit 0336706-expired on 05.01.2019”²⁵. Thanks to that information, the means of transportation with which the victims (witnesses) were transported and who is the possessor, who turned out to be an active member of the criminal group, was identified.

Another example is the examination of the „reply of the State Border Service of Ukraine received through the Joint Contact Point „Palanca”, letter No. 35/34-1193 of 02.02.2024, according to which the citizens of Ukraine: PR, HO, TS, TS, ZA, ZS, in the period 01.02.2022-29.01.2024, the state border of Ukraine did not cross”²⁶. Examination of the respective information proved that citizens of Ukraine did not legally cross the state border. Respectively, the versions of illegal crossing of the state border on the green zone were submitted and verified, which was later confirmed.

Another important aspect is the examination of files submitted by natural and legal

²³ Judgment of the Cahul Court, Central Office, dated 11.10.2022, issued in Case no. 1-327/2022. Available: https://jch.instante.justice.md/ro/pigd_integration/pdf/34e3cc54-5b66-4e80-a615-b5b6f892e7c4 [accessed: 06.08.2024].

²⁴ Judgment of the Cahul Court, Central Office, dated 11.10.2022, issued in Case no. 1-327/2022. Available: https://jch.instante.justice.md/ro/pigd_integration/pdf/34e3cc54-5b66-4e80-a615-b5b6f892e7c4 [accessed: 06.08.2024].

²⁵ Judgment of the Hîncești Court, Central Office, dated 21.07.2020, issued in Case no. 1-129/20. Disponibilă: https://jhn.instante.justice.md/ro/pigd_integration/pdf/80651d34-2bd4-4577-a037-74ee750d-c98f [accesată: 21.01.2024].

²⁶ Judgment of the Hîncești Court, Central Office, dated 25.07.2024, issued in Case no. 1-163/2024. Available: https://jhn.instante.justice.md/ro/pigd_integration/pdf/dd8070aa-5ca4-45c0-90df-2983ddc96251 [accessed: 11.08.2024].

persons to the General Inspectorate for Migration. The information obtained from them constitutes indisputable evidence. At the same time, the criminal prosecution body may obtain information such as: the persons who prepared the documents concerning the foreigner's invitation to the Republic of Moldova, the purpose of the foreigner's arrival (studies, visit, business, etc.), the place of accommodation, etc. In addition, due to the conflict in Ukraine, many illegal migrants entering the Republic of Moldova (legally or illegally) are asylum seekers, and a large number of them have not properly completed their files or they contain distorted data. For example, on 13.03.2020, „*the personal files Nos. 19MD002402 and 19MD002403, received from the Asylum and Integration Department of the Migration and Asylum Bureau of the MIA, were submitted for examination, referring to asylum seekers: HO and HQ. Based on the order of 13.03.2020, the seized documents were recognized and annexed to the criminal case as material evidence - documents*”²⁷. The documents submitted in the case file did not correspond, they contained information that aroused reasonable suspicion as to their authenticity, which was later confirmed by other evidence.

The examination of the information on the decryption of telephone calls and other information obtained by the prosecuting authority is the next piece of evidence to be adduced as a result of the respective procedural action. „*The information on the deciphering of telephone conversations obtained with the authorization of the investigating judge, which during the criminal prosecution were subject to examination, it was established that during the period of the commission of the crime, the defendants SZ and PV, at the same time, contacted each other by telephone for short periods of time, i.e. on 02.02.2020, while being in the same location. On the basis of the order of 18.05.2020, the transcripts of the deciphered telephone conversations in written form and placed on a CD-R medium were recognized and attached to the criminal case as material means of evidence*”²⁸.

Alt exemplu poate servi „*Procesul verbal de examinare a descifrărilor convorbirilor telefonice efectuate de pe cartelele SIM cu numerele XXX, YYY, ZZZ de la telefonul mobil cu IMEI 3542180344699300, ce aparține lui DN, ceea ce ne confirmă faptul că DN s-a folosit de nr. XXX, YYY, ZZZ, in committing the offense in the time period March-April 2011, talking with BS, BP, including on 13.02.2012 and 13.03.2012, while DN was on duty at the CCTP premises of the MIA, by tracing the signals of the calls made. The minutes of the examination of the deciphering of the phone calls made from the SIM card with the number VVV from the mobile phone with IMEI35679502319188, belonging to CO from which phone calls were made to the phone number XXX belonging to DN on 02.04.2012 and of the phone calls made from the SIM card with the number VVV from the mobile phone with IMEI 35679502319188, belonging to CO from which phone calls were made to the phone number MMM belonging to ce. BS on 15.03.2012, as well as telephone calls made from the SIM card with the number VVVV from the mobile phone with IMEI35679502319188 belonging to CO from which telephone calls were made to the telephone number KKK belonging to the mobile phone of the CO's mobile phone*

²⁷ Judgment of the Hîncești Court, Central Office, dated 21.07.2020, issued in Case no. 1-129/20. Disponibilă: https://jhn.instante.justice.md/ro/pigd_integration/pdf/80651d34-2bd4-4577-a037-74ee750dc98f [accesată: 21.01.2024].

²⁸ Judgment of the Hîncești Court, Central Office, dated 21.07.2020, issued in Case no. 1-129/20. Disponibilă: https://jhn.instante.justice.md/ro/pigd_integration/pdf/80651d34-2bd4-4577-a037-74ee750dc98f [accesată: 21.01.2024].

with IMEI35679502319188, from which telephone calls were made to the telephone number KKK belonging to the CO's mobile phone with IMEI. OV on 15.03.2012. Minutes of the examination of the information on the geographical location of the cells (antennas) located and used by the company „Orange” S.A., which found that the 3G Cosmos 31134 antenna Cosmos 3G serves Negruzzi str. 2 mun. Chisinau, and 3G antenna Telecentre 30024 serves Alecsandri Street. Minutes of the examination of the information on the geographical location of the cells (antennas) located and used by „Moldcell” S.A., which found that the 3G Cosmos antenna (3G1,2,3,4,5,6) serves Negruzzi 2 str., mun. Chisinau, and 3G antenna GAUDEG(3G1,2,3,4,4,5,6) serves Alecsandri str. 1, mun. Chisinau”²⁹. Thanks to the examination it was possible to prove the links between the perpetrators, between the perpetrators and the victims (witnesses), including the place of the meeting, the place of the meeting, the overlapping of information (the suspect and the witness were together at the same time). It should be noted that thanks to this procedural action it was possible to combat the defense versions of the perpetrators. One of the perpetrators was an employee of the Center for Combating Trafficking in Human Beings, which made the investigation complicated, but in the end, thanks to the professionalism of the prosecutor, the guilt was proved.

Search and evidence collection of objects and documents. In cases of organizing migrant smuggling, 24% of searches are carried out and 62% of evidence collections of objects and documents. The analysis carried out shows that in the cases of investigation of these crimes the search was carried out at the person's residence or where he/she had a residence visa, at the place of work of the suspect or at the premises of legal entities providing employment services abroad, operating in the tourism sector, etc. Searches are also carried out to detect victims temporarily staying in hotels, houses, apartments, etc., as well as the suspected persons who organized their migrant smuggling.

For example, in a criminal case in which criminal proceedings were initiated on the fact of organizing migrant smuggling committed by an organized criminal group, following the search carried out on 13.03.2016 in apartment no. XXX, located in mun. Chisinau, bd. Ștefan cel Mare și Sfânt, 6, a group of four persons of Afro-Asian origin and a citizen of Norway, identified as SK, who turned out to be an active member of the organized criminal group, was detected. The apartment in question was a temporary shelter for victims of migrant smuggling, who were in hiding and awaiting orders to migrate illegally to EU countries³⁰.

²⁹ Botanica Court, mun. Chisinau, dated 19.03.2015, issued in case no. 1280/14. Disponibilă: https://jc.instante.justice.md/ro/pigd_integration/pdf/83d102bb-49ce-e411-b888-005056a5d154 [accesată: 18.04.2024].

³⁰ Criminal case no. 2016872026, in which the criminal prosecution was initiated on 10.03.2016, on the basis of Art. 362/1, para. (3), letter a) of the Criminal Code, by the prosecution body of the Ministry of Internal Affairs, established within the Border Police Department. The criminal case in question was initiated on the organization, for the purpose of obtaining, directly or indirectly, a financial or material benefit, of the illegal entry, stay, transit through or exit from the territory of the Republic of Moldova of persons from Sri Lanka, who are neither citizens nor residents of the Republic of Moldova, committed by an organized criminal group, with the aim of reaching the European Union through transit through our country. During the criminal prosecution, it was established that the organized criminal group is composed of citizens of the Republic of Moldova, Ukraine, Romania, Norway, Russia and others, which have not been established by the prosecuting body. Thus, citizens of the Republic of Moldova VR and CO in the time period December 2015 - January 2016, being in or. Chernivtsi, Ukraine, at the instigation of the

The peculiarity of searches in these cases is that special attention must be paid to discovering, fixing and seizing almost all the documents necessary for entry into the territory of the Republic of Moldova, transit and confirmation of the legality of stay in the country; objects used for their manufacture, as well as computers and IT equipment. They usually play a significant role in establishing the fact of organized migrant smuggling.

For example, in the criminal case³¹ in which the criminal prosecution was initiated

citizen of Ukraine MP, originating from Sri Lanka, together with him, as well as with the participation of the citizen of Norway SK, with the purpose of obtaining financial benefits, created and implemented the scheme of activity of the group formed for the purpose of organizing illegal entry, stay and transit of the state territory of a group of persons originating from Sri Lanka, who are neither citizens nor residents of the R. Moldova, the exact number of which has not been established, contributing to their illegal migration from Ukraine to the Republic of Moldova during the unspecified period of time, with the help of several members of the organized criminal group, which included citizens of the Republic of Moldova NI and CV. When carrying out the illegal migration in stages, on 12.03.2016 at about 17:30 cet. NI, together with CV, through hidden places, transported a group of four persons of Afro-Asian origin from Sri Lanka to the green border on the segment served by the SPF „Stoianovca” in the direction of s. Ghioltosu Moldova - s. Ranesti Romania, where in connection with other foreign persons who were to take over the group of migrants across the state border of the Republic of Moldova, they transported the group of migrants to the green border on the segment served by the SPF „Stoianovca” in the direction of s. Ghioltosu Moldova - s. Ranesti Romania. Moldova in Romania, they entered on foot in the region of the border sign 1243 of the border area, with the final aim of ensuring their illegal migration to Romania in order to reach other countries of the European Union by illegal exit from the territory of the Republic of Moldova. Subsequently, on 12.03.2016, at around 22:00, at the intervention of border police representatives, near the village of Ghioltosu r. Cantemir, on the direction s/f 1243, were detained Cet. NI and four citizens of the island of Sri Lanka, who intended to illegally cross the state border from the Republic of Moldova to Romania with the aim of illegal migration to the European Union. On 13.03.2016 in apartment no. XXX located in mun. Chisinau bd. Ștefan cel Mare și Sfânt, 6, a group of four persons of Afro-Asian origin and Cet. SK - a citizen of Norway, who turned out to be another active member of the organized criminal group, where non-resident persons were being silenced and waiting for illegal migration by this organized criminal group. It was also established that Cet. SK entered the territory of the Republic of Moldova together with another Moldovan citizen, CO, with the latter's personal automobile. It was later established that CO is also an active member of the criminal group. At the same time, another citizen of Moldova, VR, being outside the territory of the country in the period of time from January - March 2016 coordinated the activity of organizing illegal migration of the above-mentioned citizens, coordinating through electronic means of communication the activity of the group, communicating with CO and SK, thus ensuring the functioning of the criminal group, coordinating the actions of each member and migrants, as well as persons from Romania who were supposed to pick up persons originating from Sri Lanka. At the same time, on March 15, 2016, during the on-the-spot investigation conducted in a hotel in mun. Chisinau, 3 other persons of Sri Lankan origin were detected, who were brought to the territory of the Republic of Moldova through the Chisinau International Airport, by legal means, by this organized criminal group. Also during the criminal prosecution, the organizer of this crime, who was financing the members of the criminal group, was also established through the procedural actions and special investigative measures. The organizer, named MP, a Norwegian citizen, remunerated the members of the criminal group by means of money transfers at each stage of the crime and at the same time directed the actions of each member.

³¹ Judgment of the Chisinau District Court, Central Office, dated 23.06.2017, issued in Case no. 1-272/17. Disponibilă: https://jc.instante.justice.md/ro/pigd_integration/pdf/3eb532dc-0758-e711-80d3-0050568b4c47 [accesată: 02.011.2023]. According to the materials of the criminal case, in the time period of 2013-2015, the citizen of Iraq, XXXX, being on the territory of the Republic of Moldova, pursuing the purpose of directly obtaining financial benefit from the organization of illegal entry, transit and illegal stay on the territory of other states of citizens of Iraq, India and other states, in advance, for the commission of the mentioned action (organization of illegal migration), created a stable meeting of persons with the composition: ZZZ, CCC, VVV, VVV and other persons not established by the prosecutor's body, attracting the legal entity

on the fact of organizing migrant smuggling committed by an organized criminal group. On 06.05.2016, a search was carried out at the residence XXXX, located in mun. Chisinau, MMM St., during which several notebooks, cell phones, SIM cards were found and seized. At the same time, a number of documents were also seized, as well as folders with accounts of some commercial companies, documents on the establishment of legal entities created, according to the materials of the criminal case, fictitiously, only to ensure the organization of migrant smuggling of foreigners from Iraq and other countries by members of the organized criminal group. Documents in the name of YYY with photos, identity cards were found and seized.

The analysis carried out shows that during the search for these types of offenses, the prosecutor must discover and collect the following objects and documents:

- Migration application forms, passports, work permits, work permits for immigrants, temporary residence permits;
- printed with seals and stamps for document production, service documentation;
- travel documents and tickets, boarding passes, receipts, luggage tags, coupons, tourist tours purchased in the name of immigrants;
- floppy disks, records, fax machines, mobile phones, radios, etc.;
- credit cards, money transfer receipts, documents relating to financial and commercial transactions;
- various payment ledgers, account books and documents related to the daily organization of the immigrants' work;
- documents related to visas, registration, passports;
- documents relating to the rental of premises where immigrants have lived;
- orders, employment contracts with foreign employees, work instructions, payment orders;
- advertising materials on services for issuing the above-mentioned documents, as well as registration, obtaining citizenship, residence permit;
- various equipment and objects intended for the production of these documents. First of all, computer mainframes, printers, printing equipment, external storage units, consumables (paper, ink, etc.).

When picking up computers and IT equipment, it is imperative that IT specialists are involved. Their involvement will enable the evidence collection of equipment that may contain essential information about owners and users. For example, in a criminal case on the organization of migrant smuggling committed by an organized criminal group³²,

ICS NNN SRL and other legal entities into the criminal activity, dividing the roles among the members of this meeting. At the same time, the organized criminal group, led by the Iraqi citizen XXXX, had a well-defined plan of criminal activity, which included several stages: identification and selection of potential migrants, collecting from them sums of money in the amount of 1500-2000 euro for organizing illegal entry and stay on the territory of the Republic of Moldova and the member countries of the Shengen area and fraudulently obtaining documents, on the basis of which they then applied for entry and residence visas on the territory of the member countries of the Shengen area. Through the legal entity ICS NNN SRL, the General Inspectorate for Migration requested from the General Inspectorate for Migration the release of fictitious private invitations necessary for obtaining entry and residence visas for the Republic of Moldova, using the fictitious pretext that he was inviting them on a private visit, he knew for certain that the invited persons did not know him, and the purpose of the invitations was distorted.

³² Judgment of Chisinau District Court, Central Office, dated 23.06.2017, issued in Case No. 1-272/17. Disponi-

thanks to the involvement of these specialists, the computer technology (notebooks and mobile phones) was correctly seized, which allowed to prove the involvement of members of the criminal group in the commission of the crime.

At the same time, it is worth mentioning that these specialists can recover data stored in email archives, on hard disks, floppy disks and other types of disks.

It is essential to follow the rules for picking up, packing, transporting and storing documents and items seized, as mistakes can lead to the irretrievable loss of important evidentiary information. Thus, money and documents seized during the search must be packed separately, with each document placed in a clean, dry envelope. The confiscated cell phone should be packed in a rigid cardboard box to prevent any tampering through the packaging. It should be examined either at the place of evidence collection (if there is proper authorization from the investigating judge or permission from the owner or possessor) or immediately afterwards to check the contact list, photos, SMS messages, to prevent the destruction of information on the phone in case it is disconnected.

An eloquent example is the case when, in compliance with the indicated conditions, during the search at the suspect's home, the mobile phone model „Nokia E51” with IMEI no. 35679550223191880 and SIM card no. XXXXXXXXXX was found and seized. Upon examination of the phone, the list of contacts and calls was checked, which proved its use by the suspect, contact and discussions with victims of the organization of migrant smuggling, and this fact was admitted as evidence in the guilt of the defendant³³.

An important aspect of searches is that the prosecuting authority may also carry out a body search without a separate warrant. According to Art. 130 para. (2) (3) CPP, „if there are sufficient grounds to assume that the person present in the room where the search or search is being carried out may be carrying documents or other objects that may be of evidentiary importance in the criminal case”.

For example, during a search of the suspected organizer of migrant smuggling's home, the criminal prosecution body found grounds to conduct a body search. As a result of the search, a mobile phone was found and taken from the suspect, which was used by him in discussions with the parties on the case file, in committing the crime³⁴.

In one criminal case³⁵, the guilt of the defendants was proved on the basis of statements and documents seized and examined. The action of evidence collection of documents constituted 82% of the number of procedural actions carried out in the case. Thus, „the defendant LG, holding the position of administrator of the LLC „GP”, based in XXX, which has as its main object of activity: tourism activity, activity related to the employment of citizens in the country and (or) abroad, in June 2012, in complicity with ȘN, who was employed

bilă: https://jc.instante.justice.md/ro/pigd_integration/pdf/3eb532dc-0758-e711-80d3-0050568b4c47 [accesată: 02.11.2023].

³³ Botanica Court, mun. Chisinau, dated 19.03.2015, issued in Case no. 1-280/14. Disponibilă: https://jc.instante.justice.md/ro/pigd_integration/pdf/83d102bb-49ce-e411-b888-005056a5d154 [accesată: 18.04.2024].

³⁴ Botanica Court, mun. Chisinau, dated 19.03.2015, issued in case no. 1-280/14. Disponibilă: https://jc.instante.justice.md/ro/pigd_integration/pdf/83d102bb-49ce-e411-b888-005056a5d154 [accesată: 18.04.2024].

³⁵ Judgment of the Chisinau Court, Ciocana district, dated 07.05.2019, issued in Case no. 1-613/2017. Disponibilă: https://jc.instante.justice.md/ro/pigd_integration/pdf/beb2cc16-de70-e911-80d7-0050568b021b [accesată: 07.08.2023].

as a consultant of SRL „GP”, acting intentionally, premeditatedly pursuing the purpose of organizing the migrant smuggling of VR citizens, in exchange for a direct material benefit in the amount of YYY lei, took actions on the organization of the entry, transit and illegal stay on the territory of the member countries of the Shengen area, in particular France, by obtaining on the basis of false statements the „Shengen” work visa, entry and stay on the territory of Poland as a transit country of the citizen of the Republic of Moldova VR, by submitting false data in order to conceal the real intention of entry and stay on the territory of France”.

The guilt of the defendants, including the legal entity, was proved by the following evidence obtained by the action for the evidence collection of documents: copy of the passport in the name of VR, the registration certificate of SRL „GP”, the extract from the State Register of Legal Entities issued in respect of SRL „GP”, the license issued to SRL „GP” and its annex, the act of receipt-delivery of the object of the contract of 11.06.06.2012 and the annex thereto, cash evidence collection orders with No. XXX, the contract for the provision of services No. 36 of 26.06.2012 concluded between the director of SRL „GP” and VR, the reply of the Interpol NCB No. 33/12416 of 21.12.2012, the order of appointment to office of the NQ No. 2-C of 02.05.2012, the copy of the employment record of the NQ.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In view of the above, in order to avoid the ambiguous interpretation of Article 118 of the Criminal Procedure Code, we propose the introduction of a new rule in the Criminal Procedure Act, which would define a new procedural action in its own right - the search (examination) of objects, documents (including computerized data) and official sites or any other type of electronic addresses. Thus, their search (examination) can also be carried out separately from the search (examination) within the framework of crime scene search, evidence collection, search, etc.

In cases where there are several perpetrators and victims of migrant smuggling, especially in cases where there is an intention to illegally cross the state border of the Republic of Moldova and the exact location of the crossing is unknown, we recommend involving a considerable number of law enforcement officers (border guards), due to the large area of the territory under investigation. In addition, before starting this prosecution action, it is advisable to establish a security perimeter around the place to be investigated in order to prevent attempts by illegal immigrants to flee from the place of examination, given their reluctance to contact the authorities due to their illegal presence on the territory of the country.

It is advisable that the crime scene investigation be carried out with the use of video recording or photographs, state border surveillance technique, as this allows not only more complete and objective documentation, in dynamics, of the development of the content and results of the prosecution action, but also the effective use of the obtained materials both in the analysis and evaluation of available data, as well as in the planning and implementation of the appropriate versions and actions related to their verification.

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